

Received Power and Ambient Electric Field from Broadband Emissions in Reverberant Spaces

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Abstract—The electromagnetic environment created in a reverberant space by broadband RF emissions is investigated. A white Gaussian noise source is used to emulate the wide power spectral density bandwidth, low temporal coherence time (rapid signal fluctuations), and large peak-to-average power ratio characteristics of emissions from modern digitally modulated spread-spectrum wireless networks. The interaction between the wide power spectral density of the noise signal and the highly frequency-selective channel of the reverberant space leads to average received power and average ambient electric field that exhibit very small spatial variation in the volume. This spatial uniformity in average field results from integration of the received signal power spectral density across the wide frequency bandwidth. The peak-to-average power ratio (PAPR) is derived from the time-dependent power waveform statistics of the received signal. A maximum electric field is computed from the peak received power.

I. INTRODUCTION

Recent advancements in high-speed wireless technologies offer an opportunity to enhance shipboard communications and improve operational data flow at a greatly reduced cost. Lower costs result from the minimal infrastructure required by wireless communication and sensor devices. Although these technologies have the potential of providing significant improvements in operational efficiency, there are engineering constraints in this unique multi-path environment which must be identified and controlled in order to achieve a successful deployment. These constraints arise from electromagnetic interference (EMI) to critical shipboard electronics, hazards of electromagnetic radiation to ordnance (HERO), signal coverage from access points (AP) through coupled-cavity environments, and off-hull electromagnetic emission levels (EMCON).

Measurements and analyses of new wireless data rates, modulation protocols, and transmission schemes are currently being conducted to ensure both network performance and electromagnetic compatibility in the shipboard below-deck environment [1]. The high data rates achieved by wireless networks, such as those based on IEEE 802.11 standards, utilize wide bandwidths, currently the 20 MHz and 40 MHz Wi-Fi channels and soon to reach the 80 MHz and 160 MHz WiGig channels. The dominant multi-path nature of below-deck spaces imposes severe frequency-selective fading on these broadband radio-frequency (RF) emissions [2]. The resultant ambient electromagnetic environment (EME) has

Fig. 1. Reverberation chamber test setup

been identified as a potential cause of electromagnetic interference (EMI) to co-located electronic equipments.

Previously, communications signals exhibited narrow-bandwidth spectra, and immunity testing of equipment was conducted utilizing 1-kHz wide, 80% AM-modulated test signals [3]. Recently, there has been rapidly increasing interest in characterizing equipment susceptibility to broadband signals [4], [5]. One of several difficulties in achieving this goal was identified as assessing the stressing electric field that is present inside a reverberant space given these broadband RF emissions. In this work, we investigate the effects of the reverberant channel on broadband signals and the resultant received power and ambient electric-field levels.

II. TEST PROCEDURE

The test setup, shown in Fig. 1, consists of a large reverberation chamber (222 m³), broadband signal generator (Aeroflex BSG 18-W), spectrum analyzer (R&S FSL18), E-field probe (ETS-Lindgren HI-6005), vector network analyzer (Agilent E8362B), and two double-ridged guide antennas (ETS-Lindgren 3117). The reverberation chamber is “tuned” by loading the space with absorber material so that the cavity quality factor Q is representative of values found in below-deck spaces aboard ships and submarines. The broadband

signal source is configured to produce continuous, white Gaussian noise (WGN) signals that are filtered and up-converted to the channel frequencies. The ‘white’ descriptor indicates that the power spectral density is nearly constant over the full filter bandwidth, producing a rectangular-shaped spectrum. The ‘Gaussian’ descriptor indicates that the amplitude probability density function of the signal has a normal distribution with zero mean and finite variance.

The IEEE 802.11 wireless protocol involves the digital modulation of carriers and sub-carriers in various spread spectrum schemes. The modulation types are primarily B/QPSK (bi/quad phase shift keying) and QAM (quadrature amplitude modulation), and both can be used in a single framed packet. The primary spread-spectrum transmission scheme is orthogonal frequency division multiplexing (OFDM). Presently, OFDM utilizes multiple subcarriers (64-128) that are simultaneously modulated by data and form 20-MHz and 40-MHz bandwidth communications channels. The two main frequency bands of operation are the 2.4-GHz band and the 5-GHz band.

It is recommended that electromagnetic compatibility testing of electronic equipment be conducted using a band-limited white Gaussian noise emission source in a reverberant test environment (a reverberation chamber or the actual/replicated in-situ below-deck space) [1]. Modern spread-spectrum digitally-modulated RF signals possess spectral and temporal properties that can present a more stressful waveform for interfering with electronic components and systems than can waveforms of CW, AM-modulated or pulsed signals. The wide power spectral density bandwidth, low temporal coherence time (rapid signal fluctuations), and large amplitude spikes of filtered white Gaussian noise RF emissions serve as upper-bound conditions for digitally modulated wireless RF emissions. Prior compatibility testing utilizing emissions from the actual wireless network was successful, but is costly and time-consuming, and verifies compatibility at only a single frequency and for a specific communications protocol. The development of a band-limited white Gaussian noise emission source capable of testing a wide swept-frequency range, while providing a conservative worst-case test of digital wireless signal spectra and waveforms, enables a cost-effective electromagnetic compatibility test that can be used across all platforms.

It is important to emphasize that the WGN source is not intended to duplicate or simulate RF emissions from a specific modulation/protocol. It will emulate the noise-like signal properties of existing modulation schemes in a bounding sense, with representative bandwidths, power spectral densities, peak-to-average power levels, and temporal waveforms. For this test, the measured spectral and temporal output of the WGN source is shown in Figs. 2(a) and 2(b), respectively, at 5.5 GHz for a 20-MHz channel. Actual output power levels are higher by 30 dB than those shown in the traces in Fig. 2, due to a fixed 30-dB attenuator used to make these direct source-to-receiver measurements. A similar 40-MHz channel WGN output signal is also used. Average output power in these tests is set in the range 5-10 mW.

Fig. 2. (a) Power spectral density and (b) instantaneous power waveform of 20-MHz bandwidth WGN source at 5.5 GHz. (c) CCDF statistics of time-sampled power waveform.

The complementary cumulative density function (CCDF) analysis provides average power and the probability of power exceeding a value above the mean from data samples acquired from the signal envelope power versus time waveform in Fig. 2(b). The data acquisition window provided 100,000 samples for the CCDF plot in Fig. 2(c). For semi-stochastic signals, the peak power can be defined as the power above the mean that occurs at some chosen low probability value in the plot. For example, the peak power would be expected to exceed approximately 6.5 dB above the mean with a probability of 0.01 for this white Gaussian noise signal. The WGN source has a normally distributed amplitude signal, yielding power samples that are exponentially distributed.

The transfer function gain of the reverberation chamber, which serves as a mock-up of the below-deck environment, is measured as $|S_{21}(f)|^2$ over a 100-MHz bandwidth at 5.5 GHz with the vector network analyzer and the two horn antennas. Note that the transfer function gain characterizes a linear, time-invariant network comprised of the reverberant space and the transmit/receive antennas. At a fixed chamber tuner position, the measured chamber gain is shown in Fig. 3, with the frequency-averaged gain indicated by the red line. The gain measurement is made at six different tuner positions, where the frequency-averaged gain is nearly identical in all six cases. The frequency- and spatial (tuner)- averaged value is given at -43.4 dB, corresponding to a cavity quality factor of $Q \sim 10,000$ at 5.5 GHz. Of much importance to broadband signals is the very large variation in gain over frequency (a stir ratio of 20 – 30 dB) and the very small channel decorrelation bandwidth on the order of 550 kHz.. This extreme frequency-selective channel is particularly challenging in achieving acceptable throughput performance in broadband wireless networks.

Fig. 3. Reverberation chamber gain $|S_{21}(f)|^2$ at 5.5 GHz. Red line indicates frequency-averaged value.

Fig. 4. (a) Power spectral density and (b) instantaneous power waveform of 20-MHz bandwidth received signal in reverberation chamber at 5.5 GHz. (c) CCDF statistics of time-sampled power waveform.

III. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

A. Received Power

The received power measurements are shown in Fig. 4 (not corrected for 1.2 dB loss in receive cable). In Fig. 4(a), the signal average power P_{av} is calculated from the power spectral density function as,

$$P_{av} = \int_{BW} S(\nu) d\nu \quad (1)$$

where $S(\nu)$ is the power spectral density of the signal, ν is frequency, and BW is the full noise bandwidth of the signal. This operation is performed in the spectrum analyzer software, and takes account of the actual spectral properties of the analyzer IF filter used in the measurements. The RMS detector is used to provide true average power measurements.

The communications channel imparts a transfer function gain $G_i(\nu) = |S_{21_i}(\nu)|^2$ to the transmitted power spectral density $S_T(\nu)$ according to

$$S_{R,i}(\nu) = G_i(\nu) \cdot S_T(\nu) \quad (2)$$

where $S_{R,i}(\nu)$ is the received power spectral density. The index i denotes the discrete tuner positions in the chamber. The frequency-selective fading of the chamber causes large variations in what was a nearly flat spectrum output from the WGN source – compare Fig. 4(a) with Fig. 2(a). These variations in gain, which are as large as 15-20 dB in magnitude, are caused by the frequency stirring of the modal field patterns in the chamber.

Integrating the power spectral density over the 20 MHz channel bandwidth gives the total received average power,

$$P_{R,i} = \int_{BW} S_{R,i}(\nu) d\nu = \int_{BW} G_i(\nu) \cdot S_T(\nu) d\nu \quad (3)$$

In the case of digitally modulated spread-spectrum signals in a reverberation chamber, $S_T(\nu)$ is a slowly varying function of frequency over the bandwidth BW , while $G_i(\nu)$ is a rapidly varying function of frequency at these microwave frequencies. Hence, we can approximate the integral in (3) by

$$P_{R,i} \cong \sum_j \left[S_T(\nu_j) \cdot \int_{\Delta\nu_j} G_i(\nu) d\nu \right] \quad (4)$$

$$P_{R,i} \cong \sum_j \left[S_T(\nu_j) \Delta\nu_j \cdot \frac{1}{\Delta\nu_j} \int_{\Delta\nu_j} G_i(\nu) d\nu \right] \\ = \langle G \rangle \cdot \sum_j [S_T(\nu_j) \Delta\nu_j] \quad (5)$$

where,

$$\langle G \rangle \equiv \frac{1}{\Delta\nu_j} \int_{\Delta\nu_j} G_i(\nu) d\nu \quad (6)$$

and the index j denotes a sub-interval $\Delta\nu_j$ in the channel bandwidth BW over which the power spectral density $S_T(\nu_j)$ is approximately constant. The gain $\langle G \rangle$ in (6) is an average value over frequency, and, provided this averaging is done over a sufficient frequency bandwidth $\Delta\nu_j$, is not strongly dependent on index values i and j . Performing the summation in the last term of (5), we obtain the final simple result,

$$P_R \cong \langle G \rangle \cdot P_T \quad (7)$$

Equation (7) indicates that the average receive power in the chamber is not strongly dependent on the mechanical mode stirring effect of the chamber tuners. This in turn implies that (7) holds at any spatial location within the working volume. In Table I, it can be seen that the approximation in (7) is good for both 20-MHz and 40-MHz bandwidth cases. The measured receive power P_R shown in Table I is an average taken from 26 independent tuner positions. It can be seen that the standard deviation σ in these 26 average receive powers is < 1 dB for both bandwidth cases, with the standard deviation decreasing from 0.9 dB to 0.5 dB as the signal

TABLE I
MEASURED AVERAGE TRANSMIT AND RECEIVE POWERS FOR
BROADBAND WGN EMISSIONS AT 5.5 GHz

Channel Bandwidth	20 MHz	40 MHz
Measured Transmit Power P_T	8.7 dBm	9.3 dBm
Measured Chamber Gain $\langle G \rangle$	-43.4 dB	-43.4 dB
Calculated Receive Power P_R	-34.7 dBm	-34.1 dBm
Measured Receive Power P_R	-33.9 dBm $\sigma = 0.9$ dB over 26 tuner positions	-33.4 dBm $\sigma = 0.5$ dB over 26 tuner positions

bandwidth increases. The large frequency-selective fading of 15-20 dB imposed by the chamber channel on the nearly flat spectrum output from the WGN source is largely averaged out by the integration of the receive power spectral density over the channel bandwidth. Mechanical mode stirring from the chamber tuners serves to redistribute the fading pattern throughout the channel bandwidth, but has small effect on the total integrated power across the full band. These same traits have been verified for actual 802.11(g) and (n) wireless networks operating in our reverberation chamber.

In Fig. 4(b), the instantaneous received power versus time waveform is measured. By placing the spectrum analyzer in zero-span mode with sample detection, and setting the IF bandwidth equal to the channel bandwidth (e.g., 20 MHz), we obtain time-resolved measurements of the modulated signal envelope power. The filter used for this purpose is a built-in digital channel filter with highly selective skirts.

The reverberation chamber's ability to track the time-dependent modulated signal envelope power of the source $P_T(t)$ depends on its quality factor $Q = \omega \tau$, where τ is the characteristic energy relaxation time of the space. In Fig. 2(b), rapid temporal variations in $P_T(t)$, on the scale of 100 – 200 ns, can be seen for the 20-MHz broadband signal. The received power $P_R(t)$ can be approximated by [6],

$$P_R(t) = \frac{c \lambda^2}{8 \pi} \int_0^t \frac{u^\delta(t-t')}{U_0} P_T(t') dt' \quad (8)$$

where

$$u^\delta(t) = \frac{U_0}{V} e^{-\frac{t}{\tau}}$$

The average energy density function $u^\delta(t)$ is the chamber impulse response for a δ -function excitation that delivers $U_0 = 1$ J of energy at time $t = 0$ s. As such, it is used as a Green's function kernel in (8) with the time-dependent driving function of power $P_T(t)$ injected into the cavity. Equation (8) is the convolution of the time response of a first-order low-pass filter and the noise-like time domain waveform of the stochastic source.

For below-deck spaces, Q values are typically low. For the $Q \sim 10,000$ used in these measurements at 5.5 GHz, the characteristic energy relaxation time is $\tau \sim 290$ ns. This is on the order of the scale of the temporal variations in source output power. From Figs. 4(b) and (c), it is observed that the received power waveform $P_R(t)$ seems to possess similar instantaneous power variations and CCDF power statistics as the transmit power waveform $P_T(t)$ exhibits in Figs. 2(b) and (c). The measured CCDF of $P_R(t)$ in Fig. 4(c) shows the statistical distribution of 200,000 data samples from the received power waveform in Fig. 4(b). The mean value agrees well with the value shown from the spectral plot in Fig. 4(a). The peak-to-average power ratio is approximately 6.5 dB using the 0.01 probability point on the CCDF curve.

B. Electric Field

The statistical process of calculating electric field levels from power measurements in a reverberation chamber has been rigorously investigated [7]. In general, a field component, E_z , is related to measured receive power averaged over time by,

$$\langle |E_z|^2 \rangle = \frac{320 \pi^2}{\eta_{rx} \lambda^2} \langle P_R \rangle \quad (9)$$

The receive antenna efficiency is $\eta_{rx} = 0.95$. To go a step further to arrive formally at $\langle |E_z| \rangle$, we require information about the statistical distribution of the squared magnitude of the field component over time. For the WGN source used here, an exponential distribution function is appropriate for the transmitted power waveform. The received power waveform appears to have "inherited" similar statistical distribution properties, as the low-pass filtering effect of the reverberant space is not prevalent in this case. The necessary math for obtaining $\langle |E_z| \rangle$ from (9) was developed previously [8], with the result well approximated by,

$$\langle |E_z| \rangle \cong \frac{8 \pi}{\lambda} \sqrt{\frac{5 \langle P_R \rangle}{\eta_{rx}}} \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2} \quad (10)$$

Fig. 5 shows the comparison of average field values computed from (10) with those measured using a single axis of the ETS-Lindgren E-field probe. The $\langle P_R \rangle$ and $\langle |E_z| \rangle$ data are measured using an antenna/spectrum analyzer and E-field probe, respectively, and are obtained at each of the 26 independent tuner positions. Measurement uncertainty is indicated by error bars at one standard deviation. Note that the receive antenna and E-field probe positions are widely separated inside the chamber, and as such, the fields are spatially uncorrelated at these two locations for a given fixed tuner position.

The comparison shows excellent agreement, with very close average values m . In addition, the relative independence of the measurements on tuner position is demonstrated by the very small standard deviations s . The standard deviations s for the fields calculated from power measurements are, of course, the same as reported above for the power measurements (0.9 dB for 20-MHz channel, 0.5 dB for 40-MHz channel). The standard deviations s for the fields measured with the E-field probe are 0.9 dB for the 20-MHz channel and 0.4 dB for the 40-MHz channel.

Measuring/calculating the peak field poses a challenge for these broadband signals. It would be difficult for E-field probe circuitry to track the rapid variations in amplitude envelope that occur during packet transmissions. However, instantaneous power measurements using fast real-time analyzers with acquisition bandwidths up to 160 MHz are quite easy. In addition, given the complexity of packet frames and the timing/duration of packet transmissions, as well as

Fig. 5. Average electric field measured using antenna/spectrum analyzer and E-field probe for (a) 20-MHz and (b) 40-MHz bandwidth signals in a reverberation chamber at 5.5 GHz.

other emissions such as beacon and probe signals in wireless networks, it is essential to be able to “see” the whole time-domain power waveforms. In this manner, the maximum power envelope of the waveforms can be determined in conjunction with using the probabilistic CCDF analysis of time-windowed data. It is then left to “equate” a maximum field $|E_z|_{Max}$ to this maximum power P_R^{Max} . In the case of WGN signals, the peak-to-average power ratio is well characterized statistically and can serve as a bounding waveform for many digitally modulated spread-spectrum waveforms. An appropriate statistical relation is given by [8],

$$(11) \quad |E_z|_{Max} \cong \frac{8\pi}{\lambda} \sqrt{\frac{5 P_R^{Max}}{\eta_{rx}}}$$

For the 20-MHz bandwidth case, the maximum power envelope is measured at $P_R^{Max} = -28.3$ dBm, with a standard deviation $\sigma = 0.7$ dB over 26 independent tuner positions. The associated peak electric field is calculated from (11) at $|E_z|_{Max} \cong 1.3$ V/m, with a standard deviation $\sigma = 0.1$ V/m (0.7 dB) over the 26 tuner positions.

IV. CONCLUSION

The electromagnetic environment created in a reverberant space by broadband RF emissions is investigated. The interaction between the wide power spectral density of the noise signal and the highly frequency-selective channel of the reverberant space leads to average received power and average ambient electric field that exhibit very small spatial variation in the volume. This spatial uniformity in average field results from integration of the received signal power spectral density across the wide frequency bandwidth. The peak-to-average power ratio (PAPR) is derived from the time-dependent power waveform statistics of the received signal. Measurements conducted with high-speed signal analyzers can resolve the complex time-domain signal packets and provide useful CCDF statistical analysis to characterize the maximum power envelope and associated maximum electric fields. Further investigations using the 40-MHz channel bandwidth signals of an 802.11n wireless network are currently underway in our reverberation chamber.

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